

EDITOInfra

European Digital Twin Ocean

Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean

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Project Acronym: EDITO-Infra

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D 6.3

Pre-operational public integrated viewer (V2)

Work Package	<i>WP6 Interactivity/VCE/Visualisation</i>
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Version	<i>2.0</i>

1. Preoperational public integrated viewer

The demonstration of the viewer, showing an example for EMODnet data, is available as movie at the following link:
[D6.3 Pre-operational public integrated viewer V2.mp4](#)